

RDM Scoping Study and Implementation Plan

An implementation project for the Institutional
Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

Federation University Australia

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About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

This project focused on a scoping study to identify current University practices, resources and infrastructure related to research data management (RDM), together with a plan to implement, achieve and monitor sustainable best practice RDM. The Scoping Study reviewed both the relevant literature and documented external practice to ascertain current best practice in RDM. The Scoping Study also sought feedback from researchers, directors of research centres, professional staff, Higher Degree Research (HDR) candidates and external experts through a range of mechanisms including surveys and semi-structured interviews with individuals. Key professional staff were also approached for background information to establish the local context for RDM. This feedback informed identification of any gaps between existing services and resources, and which communication channels may work best for different cohorts. Stakeholder feedback and input also underlies the plan for moving to best practice, which requires use of the principles of collaboration and co-design, with feedback assisting to prioritise planning steps, to identify where more extensive communication may be necessary, where skills development is required, and what opportunities may be possible for greater Directorate/School/Centre/GRS involvement, among others.

This project tested aspects of the [Institutional Underpinnings framework Culture Change element](#), in particular: defining the current state; assessing RDM-related risk; obtaining buy-in and engagement; and leveraging existing staff capability. The questions within the earlier version of the draft framework guided the feedback process, but are equally applicable within the recently revised element.

Resulting Improvements

A full review of RDM has not been done before, and the Scoping Study has identified opportunities to promote infrastructure, techniques and skills development. In addition, it has highlighted areas of inconsistent practice and misunderstanding related to RDM, its practices and its benefits. The University is presently finalising a new structure which will more firmly place research activities within the University's research centres. The learnings from this Study thus offer an opportunity to better integrate and embed RDM activities within the complete research lifecycle.

RDM implementation across the University has generally been ad hoc, with skills development planning done on an 'as time permits' basis. Allied to this, the development of university infrastructure has been uncoordinated. The research publications repository was originally acquired in 2007 as part of the national ARROW Project, and more recently, a research data repository was acquired under the leadership of the University eResearch Advisory Committee. The University research ecosystem will benefit from this review of RDM across the University and planning for implementation and monitoring of sustainable best practice RDM aligns with University research-related strategic planning. In summary, this project is fundamental to move RDM forward at the University as it will consider new models and

approaches, identify gaps and inconsistencies in present services and resources, and provide a plan of action to move to recognised best practice through a more structured, consistent and comprehensive approach.

In addition, it has prompted a review and reconsideration of the RDM information and skills training currently in place, which will facilitate higher visibility of infrastructure, assistance, processes and benefits. It has also flagged the need to review and improve communications around the data repositories and their use.

Next Steps

1. Involvement in Institutional Underpinnings Phase 3 – by contributing to refining the [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#).
2. More formal engagement with Directors of Research Services and the Graduate Research School on how best to utilise and implement some or all of the Framework elements. Particular emphasis is expected to be placed on skills development in RDM, including a discussion around how or whether this could be made mandatory for HDR candidates.
3. Greater involvement in the researcher induction process needs to be negotiated and formalised also, so that RDM becomes more explicit in University processes.
4. Comprehensive review of relevant policies and procedures to ensure alignment with best practice as articulated in the Framework and in response to researcher and professional staff feedback obtained during the Phase 2 testing at Federation University.
5. Active collaboration with HDR supervisors and their candidates as a group. Thus provides greater opportunities for discussion, reinforcement and peer support for managing research data well. In addition, provision of discipline and time-contextualised advice and information is likely to promote a more engaged response.
6. Risk related to RDM appears to not be well articulated in policy or procedure, or in terms of operational responsibilities, and is a concept which is likely to resonate and be engaged with at the institutional level. Explicit strategies to identify and manage risk are needed: reputational, funder, researcher attraction and appointment, and HDR candidate attraction and enrolment.

Project Outputs

Reusable outputs produced include:

1. Methodological components developed for use in the Scoping Study, which comprise: a survey of researchers and relevant professional staff; and the semi-structured interview guide.

2. A formal response to be incorporated into the national RDM Framework Culture Change element, in particular regarding: defining the current state; assessing RDM-related risk; obtaining buy-in and engagement; and leveraging existing staff capability, together with recommendations.

Survey: <https://doi.org/10.25955/21442977.v1>

Interview questions: <https://doi.org/10.25955/21442962.v1>

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).